

Kinetics of Aquation of Chloropenta-amminecobalt(III) perchlorate in Dicarboxylate Solutions Containing 10% Ethanol at 40°

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A new empirical correlation between the observed first order rate constant, k_{obs} , and the stoichiometric concentrations of the dicarboxylate anions, C_L , was obtained in the aquation of chloropenta-amminecobalt(III) perchlorate at 40° in six different dicarboxylate solutions containing 10% ethanol. It takes the form

$$k_{obs} = k_0 + c/d[(k_{obs})_{max} - k_0] \cdot C_L$$

where c and d are empirical constants of values 7.4×10^{-6} and 11.8×10^{-7} , respectively. A reaction mechanism which would explain the above equation was investigated.

DESPITE the observation that ion-association is kinetically significant in solution, there are relatively few studies on the kinetic nature of ion-paired entities. Laurie and Monk¹ and Campbell² used the interpretation of Wyatt and Davies³ in studying the aquation of halogenopenta-amminecobalt(III) ions in various salt solutions, for which the ion-pairs were kinetically more labile than the positive free cation in aquation. An identical treatment was applied by Walker and Monk⁴ to the more reactive chromium. Solvent-assisted dissociation was the model proposed⁵ for the aquation of chloro- and bromopenta-amminechromium(III) ions in aqueous dicarboxylate solutions.

Recently, Amira, Monk and Carpenter⁶ studied the kinetics of aquation of chloro- and bromopenta-amminecobalt(III) complexes in 10% ethanolic dicarboxylate solutions, since greater ion-association takes place in this solvent. The present work is an extended study of the aquation of chloropenta-amminecobalt(III) cation in 10% ethanolic dicarboxylate solutions of different dicarboxylate concentrations in an attempt to obtain a new empirical correlation between the stoichiometric dicarboxylate anions and the different forms of the rate constants.

Experimental

Succinic, malic, tartaric, malonic and maleic acids, sodium hydroxide and potassium hydrogen phthalate used were of AnalaR grade. The purity of

the acids was checked by elemental analysis before making stock solutions of the ion-pairing ligands. Chloropenta-amminecobalt(III) nitrate was prepared as recommended⁷ and converted to the perchlorate salt by precipitation from a warm acidified concentrated solution of LiClO_4 by cooling in ice-water. The product was washed with alcohol and ether till free from acid and then dried at 110°.

The rate of aquation was followed by the potentiometric titration of the released chloride ions⁸ using timed samples cooled in ice-water. This method of analysis was found to be as good as spectrophotometric and e.m.f. methods⁹.

Results and Discussion

The values of the observed first order rate constants, k_{obs} , were calculated from the potentiometric titration readings by the linear least mean square analysis of $\ln \frac{V_\infty}{(V_\infty - V_t)}$ (V_t = titre at time t and V_∞ = infinity titre).

The dissociation constants, K , of the ion-pairs formed between the complex cation and the dicarboxylate anions in 10% ethanol were previously determined⁶ using the cell: glass electrode/ $\text{H}_2\text{L}(\text{C}_L)$, NaOH (m_1), complex perchlorate (m_2)/calomel electrode. However, the first and second dissociation constants (K_1 and K_2) of the dicarboxylic acids (H_2L) used were previously determined by Monk

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TABLE I—VALUES OF k_{obs} AT DIFFERENT BUFFER COMPOSITION AND IN DIFFERENT DICARBOXYLATE MEDIA AT 40° ($10^4 k_o = 5.68 \pm 0.15 \text{ min}^{-1}$)

$10^4 [\text{NaOH}]$ M	$10^4 [\text{Acid}] (M)$ $= O_L$	$10^4 k_{obs} (\text{min}^{-1})$					
		Succinate	Malate	Tartrate	Malonate	Maleate	Phthalate*
5.06	4.02	6.00 ± 0.1	6.45 ± 0.15	6.35 ± 0.20	6.75 ± 0.30	7.49 ± 0.40	9.11 ± 0.15
12.11	7.26	6.02 ± 0.30	7.15 ± 0.15	7.10 ± 0.10	7.61 ± 0.25	8.80 ± 0.20	11.12 ± 0.30
18.17	10.99	6.62 ± 0.30	6.75 ± 0.15	6.90 ± 0.10	7.85 ± 0.30	11.20 ± 0.10	14.40 ± 0.40
24.23	14.53	6.98 ± 0.30	7.50 ± 0.20	7.80 ± 0.20	8.90 ± 0.15	12.10 ± 0.10	15.20 ± 0.30
27.26	16.35	7.05 ± 0.10	7.40 ± 0.30	—	8.88 ± 0.40	13.20 ± 0.10	14.50 ± 0.11
36.34	21.79	7.67 ± 0.10	8.70 ± 0.20	8.90 ± 0.20	9.60 ± 0.10	13.40 ± 0.50	15.70 ± 0.50
40.00	24.54	7.92 ± 0.30	7.70 ± 0.30	7.70 ± 0.10	9.51 ± 0.50	13.80 ± 0.30	17.30 ± 0.30
45.00	26.00	7.03 ± 0.40	9.00 ± 0.20	8.50 ± 0.20	9.48 ± 0.40	14.10 ± 0.10	16.20 ± 0.40
50.00	40.00	6.95 ± 0.20	7.90 ± 0.10	8.10 ± 0.20	9.58 ± 0.20	13.70 ± 0.10	15.50 ± 0.40
55.00	43.32	7.47 ± 0.10	—	5.30 ± 0.40	9.42 ± 0.20	13.80 ± 0.60	16.60 ± 0.70
60.00	48.00	7.58 ± 0.30	8.50 ± 0.10	8.40 ± 0.10	9.52 ± 0.30	13.70 ± 0.40	16.30 ± 0.30
68.00	45.00	7.65 ± 0.60	7.70 ± 0.30	8.40 ± 0.15	9.48 ± 0.25	13.40 ± 0.30	16.40 ± 0.30
76.00	48.00	7.77 ± 0.20	8.70 ± 0.50	8.50 ± 0.20	9.55 ± 0.40	13.70 ± 0.70	18.00 ± 0.90

* Potassium hydrogen phthalate was used with half [NaOH] given in the table.

and Amira⁹ using the principle of their published method¹⁰.

Six different types of dicarboxylate solutions containing 10% ethanol over a wide stoichiometric concentration range of the ion-pairing ligands, C_L , were used in order to fulfill the requirement of the present work. The kinetic data are listed in Table I. The observed first order rate constants, k_{obs} , were plotted against C_L for the different ion-pairing ligands at 40° (Fig. 1). It is clear from this figure that linear plots radiating from the same point are

Fig. 1. Plots of k_{obs} against C_L values for different dicarboxylates.

obtained at lower and moderate values of C_L ; the intercept being equal to the uncatalytic rate constant k_o . The slope values, b , of these plots increase from succinate to phthalate (malate and tartrate have nearly the same value). The plot of b values vs the ion-pairing thermodynamic association constants K_{ass} (Fig. 2) gives straight lines passing through the origin with a slope, c , equal to 7.40×10^{-6} .

Fig. 2. Plot of $10^3(b)$ vs K_{ass} values.

The above findings can be represented mathematically as:

$$k_{obs} = k_o + bC_L$$

$$b = cK_{ass}$$

i.e., $k_{obs} = k_o + cK_{ass}C_L$ (1)

It is clear from Table I that k_{obs} attains more or less constant value from which the corresponding $(k_{obs})_{max}$ value was determined for each ion-pairing ligand used (Table 2). The variation of $(k_{obs})_{max}$ with K_{ass} is a straight line relationship (Fig. 3) with an intercept equal to k_o and a positive slope, d of 11.8×10^{-7} . Hence,

$$(k_{obs})_{max} = k_o + dK_{ass} \quad (2)$$

From equations 1 and 2 the new empirical correlation can be represented as,

$$k_{obs} = k_o + c/d[(k_{obs})_{max} - k_o]C_L \quad (3)$$

Garrick^{11,12} found that the rate of aqutation of chloropenta-amminecobalt(III) ion is slightly increased by univalent anions as chloride, nitrate, chlorate and formate. He expressed his results empirically as,

$$k_{obs} = k_o + k_L C_L \quad (4)$$

(k_L is the catalytic coefficient)

TABLE 2—VALUES OF $(k_{\text{obs}})_{\text{max}}$ AND K_{ass} FOR DIFFERENT DICARBOXYLATE MEDIA AT 40°

	Succinate	Malate	Tartrate	Malonate	Maleate	Phthalate
K_{ass}^*	158.7	185.2	250.0	285.7	666.7	909.1
$10^4(k_{\text{obs}})_{\text{max}}$	7.50	7.90	8.50	9.10	13.80	16.40

* The values of K_{ass} are taken from reference 6.

Fig. 3. Plot of $(k_{\text{obs}})_{\text{max}}$ against K_{ass} values.

In case of chromium complex analogue, the same conclusion has been reached by Jones, Harris and Wallace⁶, although they did not offer similar explanation for aquation process in aqueous dicarboxylate media. This can be overcome by the aid of the new empirical correlation (equation 3) but in a new dicarboxylate medium containing 10% ethanol which favoured the condition for highlighting any connection among the kinetic parameters affecting reaction rate. Also, equation (3) can explain the Garric empirical equation (equation 4) in which the catalytic coefficient k_L can be compared to $c/d [(k_{\text{obs}})_{\text{max}} - k_0]$ in our work.

The following proposed reaction mechanism can explain the empirical equation 3 :

(K is the concentration association constant)

The overall rate aquation can be represented as,

$$k_{\text{obs}} \cdot C = k_0[\text{Cp}^{2+}] + k[\text{CpL}] \quad \dots \text{ (5)}$$

$$\text{where } C = [\text{Cp}^{2+}] + [\text{CpL}] \quad \dots \text{ (6)}$$

$$\text{and } K = \frac{[\text{CpL}]}{[\text{Cp}^{2+}][\text{L}^{2-}]} \quad \dots \text{ (7)}$$

Substituting from equations 6 and 7 in equation 5 one can find

$$k_{\text{obs}} C = k_0(C - [\text{CpL}]) + kK(C - [\text{CpL}])[\text{L}^{2-}] \quad \text{ (8)}$$

Knowing that $C \gg [\text{CpL}]$ and $[\text{L}^{2-}] \approx \text{C}_L$, equation (8) takes the form

$$k_{\text{obs}} C = k_0 C + kK C_L C$$

$$\text{or } k_{\text{obs}} = k_0 + kK C_L \quad \dots \text{ (9)}$$

The last equation can be compared with both equations 3 and 4.

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